

The Use of KWL (Know – Want to Know – Learned) Strategy for Reading Comprehension in Blended Learning

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ABSTRACT : Reading comprehension is a complex process among the readers and the texts. Because of its complexity, students often encounter difficulties in comprehending a reading text. Although a lot of studies have been conducted in teaching reading comprehension, this present study offers another method to apply. The purpose of this research is to examine the effectiveness of KWL strategy in blended learning method. Quasi experimental (nonequivalent pretest and posttest control-group design) was used as the research design. The population of this study was all tenth-grade students in Senior High School 5 Kendari. The researcher chose a purposive method as a sample technique which determined *class science*—class X.SCIENCE.4 (n=30) as experimental group and class X.SCIENCE.5 (n=30) as control group. Researcher applied *KWL strategy in blended learning method* in experiment class and *Conventional Method* in control class. A recount text (including finding out the main idea and supporting details) was used as a media to measure students' reading comprehension. The collected data were analyzed by using descriptive statistic (mean, standard deviation, median, mode, minimum and maximum), inferential statistic (paired and independent sample t test), *N-gain* and *Effect Size*. The finding of this research was students' scores on reading comprehension of experimental group were higher than students' reading scores in control group. It can be concluded that the KWL strategy in blended learning was effective to use in improving students' reading comprehension and recommended to be applied in eleventh and twelfth grade of Senior High School students.

KEYWORDS -Blended Learning, KWL Strategy, Reading Comprehension

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology has developed quickly in various sector lives which it is no longer an intimidating novelty. It is not only used both in business and industry, but also broadcast into the teaching world. The educators must recognize that students now become technologically skilled. Technology can be applied into school or classroom activity through many ways and one of them is by applying blended learning method. Blended learning is a method which combines both face-to-face classroom interaction and online learning. Blended learning can be used in all subjects in any kind of schools as long as the school can utilize and provide the technology facilities and network to access internet. One of subjects that need a big attention from the teachers is reading skill. As a skill in language learning, reading offers many people in the world to know others' idea about several things as a way to communicate indirectly with some distances[1]. They further said that reading basically means pronouncing the word loudly and understanding the idea conveyed in the text. It means that reading not only tells about how to recognize some codes and know how to pronounce it, but also emphasizes about how to comprehend the meaning of the text.

It proves that comprehending the text is essential to master reading. Comprehension is an essential in reading, whereas the reader should understand what they read. Knowing how to read yet have no idea about what they are reading is not synchronized with the idea of the language that is used to communicate. It means, without the ability of comprehending the text, the purpose of reading, which transfers knowledge to the readers cannot be fulfilled [2].

As mentioned in the curriculum of 2013, students in Senior High Schools should be taught reading comprehension embedded with other elements of reading skill. They cannot only pronounce and remember the vocabularies in English, but also have to know the ideas conveyed in the text both explicit and implicit. Curriculum of 2013 also requires the senior high students to achieve the minimum passing score (KKM) which has been set by the school. The writer proposed a learning strategy, *Know-Want-Learned* (KWL) strategy, to be applied in order to increase students' reading achievement. This strategy is assumed can improve students reading comprehension ability by focusing on the process of reading itself.

According to NSW Country Areas Program which has discussed about the blended learning environment and the development of teaching quality by utilizing blended learning into classroom activities, a blended learning approach allows teachers to blend Quality Teaching practices with the increasing availability of contemporary ICTs and appropriate technological hardware within classroom environment. In this case, the teachers can modify the activities in the classroom by applying KWL strategy into a blended learning method in order to the learning process can be running well and pleasure. KWL is one of the active learning strategies which shows the students as the center of the learning process in the classroom, or in other word, students will be more active than the teachers [3].

Ogle stated that in the KWL, the students are trained how to learn from the texts that involves three cognitive steps: assessing what student's know, what student's want to find out, and what student's learn[4]. Fengjuan said that the Know-Want-Learned (KWL) strategy is an instructional reading strategy that widely used to teach reading classes in the USA. Thus, this strategy brings the expectation to increase students' achievement also in Indonesia[5]. Youniss explained that KWL strategy helps the pupils become better readers by drawing them to do many things that good readers do. He further said that this strategy gets the students to read silently with comprehension, focusing to the learning process where the students are supposed to explore their reading process by thinking about what they know, what they want to know, and what they have learnt[6].

The purpose of reading is comprehension. It means that the readers or the students should be able to understand what they read. But the fact shows that many students cannot understand the materials they read well. There are some factors that cause the difficulty in comprehending the text, such as the materials are too difficult, the lack of vocabulary, lack of background knowledge, and the readers or students do not have the purpose of reading. Therefore, the researcher attempted to use the KWL Strategy in teaching reading at SMAN 5 Kendari to know whether or not KWL Strategy in blended learning could affect the students' reading comprehension achievement.

1.1. Objective of the study

Accordance with applying of KWL strategy into reading comprehension, this paper aims to:

1. Highlight the effectiveness of the role of two learning methods, blended-learning and KWL strategy on students' reading comprehension.
2. To bring out and apply blended-learning for English teachers in SMAN 5 Kendari, particularly in teaching and learning process in the course of study.
3. To assist the teachers to develop techniques in teaching reading by using blended-learning and KWL strategy.
4. To help the students in order to be more attractive, creative and active to learn subjects, particularly for English subject by using blended-learning and KWL strategy.
5. Find out the students' feedback toward teaching quality and effectiveness in teaching reading by using the KWL strategy in blended learning method.

1.2. Significance of the study

This paper supposedly can give at least two contributions:

1. Theoretically, the result of this study can be used as an additional resource for other studies that investigate about KWL strategy in blended learning and contribute to develop the theories of English language learning particularly for increasing the use of technology in teaching and learning process.
1. Practically, it can help both teachers and students in SMAN 5 Kendari to use technology to improve English language skill in terms of reading skill. Moreover, as the instruction sources for the other learnings to apply an active learning strategy in order for teaching and learning process can be running effectively and efficiently.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a mix method design in which combine quantitative and qualitative study. The design of this study is quasi-experimental which use a nonequivalent (pretest and posttest) control-group design. This design which is divided into two groups namely experimental group and control group. The technique of taking sample of this study was purposive sampling. It means that, determining the sampling class is based on the purpose of the study. The students' placement in every class is not based on students' point or proficiency level when they were enrolled to their class. By using this technique, the researcher chooses the Class X.SCIENCE.4 as the experimental class and X.SCIENCE.5 as the control class.

2.1. Instrument of the Study

The researcher prepares some instruments to analyze the students' reading comprehension and to find out the students' feedback toward the use of KWL strategy in blended learning method.

2.1.1. The Achievement Test

The researcher develops an achievement test to measure the students' reading comprehension before and after the treatment. The students would be given a reading test before giving a treatment and the same questions used in post-test as well.

2.1.2. Questionnaire

The researcher adapted the questionnaire from the SEEQ instrument [7]. SEEQ which stands for *Student Evaluation of Educational Quality* is an instrument used to obtain students' feedback on teaching quality and effectiveness. SEEQ is an easy way to obtain feedback on teaching with demonstrated effectiveness in improving teaching quality and students' learning experience. It also increases student involvement in the education process.

2.1.3. Edmodo program instructional

Edmodo is an online networking application for teachers and students. Think Facebook, but in a safe and controlled environment appropriate for school. Edmodo is primarily a tool for within-class communication, but it also provides several ways for teachers to connect with other teachers. Over 500,000 students are using Edmodo worldwide. The researcher uses LMS namely Edmodo as online tool in blended learning to complete a KWL strategy.

2.2. Procedure of Data Collection

The suggested procedures for experimental group were:

1. Pre-test. Pre-test aimed to know the students' reading comprehension before being given the treatment.
2. Before begin the treatment, the researcher explained or introduced first the steps how to use the Edmodo program.
3. Treatment. Giving treatment means that all the learning activities in the experimental class will use KWL Strategy in blended learning.
4. Post Test. It is aimed to know the students' reading comprehension after giving the treatment.

Meanwhile, the procedures in the control class were:

1. Pre-test. Students have to follow the pre-test to measure students' prior knowledge about reading text (recount text, main idea, and supporting details).
2. Teaching the students by using conventional method for three times meetings.
3. Post Test. It is aimed to know the students' reading comprehension after they are taught using conventional method (lecture).

2.3. Technique of Data Analysis

To process the data is used two main techniques:

Descriptive statistics is used to test the collected data such as pre and post tests score in term of mean, mode, range, standard deviation, maximum score, minimum score and all elements which related to parametric statistic.

To test the hypothesis, the researcher used inferential statistic. Inferential statistic in this study used two kinds of test: paired sample t-test and independent sample t test.

Effect size of independent sample test, to see the magnitude effect of KWL in blended learning toward students' reading comprehension practically.

III. RESULT

After analyzing, summarizing and interpreting all data that are taken from the reading test (pre-post test), it proves that students who are taught under KWL strategy in blended learning has increased their reading comprehension scores significantly if compared with students who are taught under conventional method (lecture). In other word, the students' reading comprehension scores of experimental group are higher than students' reading comprehension scores of control group. The purpose of this study is to find out whether the application of KWL strategy in blended learning method improves students reading comprehension or not by using recount text in ways of finding the main idea and supporting details/specific information. The results have showed a significantly difference in reading scores between experimental group and control group after testing all data to find out the answer of the hypothesis. To test the hypothesis, the researcher used two kinds of test namely paired sample t test and independent sample t test.

The paired sample t test (within one group) is used to test the hypothesis by comparing the means of two variables in one group. The paired sample t test having purpose to compare the result test before and after treatment in each group, experimental group and control group. Students in the experimental class had done the pre and post test in reading comprehension.

Table 4.1 Paires Samples Test for experiment

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pre-posttest in Experiment	-28,448	29	,000

The table shows that the probability (p) values or sig. (2 tailed) is 0.000. The sig. value is less than 0.05 at significant level 5% ($0.000 < 0.05$). It means that the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected so that there is a significant score difference on students' reading comprehension before and after they are taught by using the KWL strategy in blended learning method.

Table 4.2 Paires Samples Test for control

	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pre-posttest in Experiment	-15,297	29	,000

Students in the control class also had joined the pre and post test (the reading test used in control group is same with experimental group). The probability (p) values or sig. (2 tailed) is 0.000. The sig. value is less than 0.05 at significant level 5% ($0.000 < 0.05$). It means that the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, and it can be concluded that there is a significant score difference on students' reading comprehension before and after they are taught by using conventional method (lecture).

The independent sample t test (between two groups, experiment group-control group) is used to test the hypothesis by comparing the gain score of each group.

Table 4.3 Independent Sample Test

		Levene's test (F)	t	df	Mean Difference	Sig. (2-tailed)
GAINSCORE	<i>Equal variances assumed</i>	-15,297	13,558	29	11,52000	,000

Based on the data output, the probability (p) value or sig. (2 tailed) is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Since the Asymp.sig value is less than the alpha value at the level significance 0.05, it means that the null hypothesis (H₀) was rejected and it can be concluded that there is a significant score difference on students' reading comprehension who are taught by using the KWL strategy in blended learning method and students' reading comprehension who are taught by using conventional method.

In addition, the differences between students in *experimental group* and *control group* are also seen from the Effect Size (ES). The *Effect Size* is a measure of the magnitude of the effect of one variable (Independent variable) to another variable (dependent variable), the magnitude of the difference or the relationship, which is independent of the effect of the sample size. The *effect size* is a simple way of quantifying the difference between two groups that has many advantages over the use of tests of statistical significance alone. Effect size emphasises the size of the difference rather than confounding this with sample size.

Table 4.4 EffectSize

Dependentvariable: Gain Score	MeanSquare	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared (η^2)
GROUPS	1990.656	183.810	0.000	0.760

Based on the data result show that the partial eta squared (η^2) or the Effect Size in Cohen's standard is **0.760**. It means that the average of experimental group of two standard deviations is higher than the average of control group in terms of reading comprehension scores. This shows a large difference in practice. It indicates that the use of KWL strategy in blended learning can affect learning outcomes (reading comprehension) for the students are as much as 76%.

IV. DISCUSSION

Generally, the purpose of this study is to find out the effectiveness of KWL strategy if it is combined with blended learning in reading comprehension. Both KWL and blended learning are not the new terms in the education world. KWL stands for *Know-Want to Know-Learned* is a strategy in learning reading. KWL in general has three stages to be applied. In this study, the writer used a blended learning method as one of the technologies that are mostly used by the teachers to deliver the materials. A blended learning presents a method that utilize technology with system computer. Blended learning is a method when the instructor tries to combine both face-to-face classroom interaction and online means. According to NSW Country Areas Program (2010) stated that the use of blended learning and the development of teaching quality by utilizing blended learning into classroom activities. Blended learning approach allows teacher to blend Quality Teaching Practice with the increasing availability of contemporary ICTs and appropriate technological hardware within classroom environment. In this case, the development teaching in this study is the researcher utilizes a technology by modifying the activities in the classroom through KWL strategy into blended learning method in order to learning process can be running well and pleasure. Although the result of this study showed positive effect toward reading comprehension by using KWL in blended learning, yet there are some limitations that can be considerations for completing this research in the future. This study does not investigate factors that influence the effectiveness of KWL strategy in blended learning method for students' reading comprehension. By knowing the factors, so we know the strongnesses and weaknesses of this technique. There is no interviewing as an additional source information besides Questionnaire. Although interviewing is only used as secondary data, but it can help the researcher to interpret and give a specific description of the condition of subject research. Another limitation is this study only presents the problems' research which focused on identifying main idea and supporting details from a Recount Text. It will be better if the problems can be discussed broadly by adding the research problems in term of vocabulary, reference and inference.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of data calculation on the previous chapter, it can be concluded that the application of KWL strategy in blended learning can improve students' reading comprehension. This was proved by the students' reading scores has significantly increased from before they followed the test (pre-test) and after the test (post-test). To test the hypothesis, the researcher used paired and independent sample t test. The paired sample is used to measure the difference score between pre and post test in one group. The result showed that both students in experimental and control group have significantly increased their reading scores which the sig. score is less than the alpha value ($0.000 < 0.05$). Besides paired sample, there is independent sample to test the hypothesis between two groups by using the average of gain scores of each group. The result showed that the

probability value (sig. 2 tailed) is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). It means that the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H1) was accepted. Therefore, the conclusion is there is a significant score difference on students' reading comprehension who are taught by using the KWL strategy in blended learning method and students' reading comprehension who are taught by using conventional method. Since the hypothesis is just used to test the significance (statistical significance), so the researcher also used another test namely effect size to test the magnitude of the effect of one variable to another variable in the practice of education. The result shows that the effect size value is 0.760. to determine the magnitude of the effect, the researcher used Cohen's standard which the score 0.760 is equal with 76%. It means that the use of KWL strategy in blended learning can affect learning outcomes (reading comprehension) for the students are as much as 76%. Consequently, the data proved that the use of KWL strategy can improve 10th grade students' achievement in reading comprehension.

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